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management of agricultural soils**

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effect of organic matter inputs on N₂O
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List of Abbreviation

OM	Organic matter
CR	Crop residues
GM	Green manure
LM	Livestock manure
SL	Slurry
DI	Digestate
COM	Compost
BIO	Biochar
OM ₁	Crop residues, green manure, livestock manure, slurry, digestate, compost
OM ₂	Biochar, Compost
SD	Standard deviation
SE	Standard error
<i>n</i>	Number of studies
$\ln R$	Effect size (log response ratio)
CI	Confidence interval
C/N ratio	Carbon to nitrogen ratio

Highlights

- The effect of seven types of OM inputs were summarized by using a meta-analysis.
- There was a slight tendency to emission reduction by 10% due to OM inputs compared to inorganic N fertilizers across all studies.
- Biochar and compost significantly reduced N₂O emissions by 25-33 %.
- Other types of OM inputs had no statistically significant effect.
- The impacts of pedo-climatic factors and agronomic management practices were studied.

Abstract

The application of organic matter (OM) inputs to agricultural soils are appropriate practices to increase soil organic matter content, however, their use may cause an increase of greenhouse gas emissions. The objective of this report is to quantitatively synthesize results from field studies, which explore the effects of adding different OM inputs (crop residues, green manure, livestock manure, slurry, digestate, compost or biochar) to soil on N₂O emissions in Europe. We conducted a meta-analysis, using weighting of each study by the inverse of variance.

The collected database consists of 53 field studies, located in 46 sites across 15 European countries covering all European climate zones, from Alpine North to Mediterranean South. Annual precipitation and average annual temperature varied between 250 mm and 1300 mm, and between 4.5 °C and 19.6 °C, respectively. Diverse arable crops, mainly cereals, were cultivated in monoculture or in crop rotations on mineral soils. Cumulative N₂O emissions were monitored during periods from 30 to 1070 days in the fields that received either solely OM inputs or in combination with inorganic N fertilizers, while inorganic N fertilizers served as a control. The impact of pedo-climatic characteristics, agricultural management practices, the nature and quality of organic matter inputs on N₂O emissions were studied.

Keywords: EJPSOIL; N₂O; field studies, organic matter, climate change mitigation, pedo-climatic zones, meta-analysis

1. Introduction

The application of organic matter (OM) inputs, such as crop residues, green manure, livestock manure, slurry, digestate, compost and biochar, to agricultural soils are appropriate practices to increase soil organic matter content, as it has been demonstrated in numerous global meta-analyses and reviews (Xia et al., 2018; Bolinder et al., 2020; Siedt et al., 2021; Tiefenbacher et al., 2021; Bai et al., 2019; Jian et al., 2020; Gross et al., 2021). Even small increases per unit area in the soil organic carbon (SOC) pool can have important positive implications in the global C balance and climate change since it may offset a significant fraction of CO₂ emissions worldwide (Guenet et al., 2021). However, mitigation effects of agricultural practices enhancing C sequestration (Cseq) can in turn be offset if nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions increase (Lugato et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2017). In contrast soil management practices enhancing Cseq and reducing non-CO₂ GHG emissions might imply a “double-win” situation, with synergetic mitigation effects on climate change. Table 1 shows the list of 16 global meta-analyses on the effect of different OM inputs on N₂O emissions, the overall effects and main moderators studied.

1.1. Crop residues

The return of crop residues (CR) to the soil is an agricultural nutrient-conserving practice that effectively increases soil fertility and crop nutrition. However, the role of CR on agroecosystem N cycle is not well quantified. The impact of CR on N₂O emissions was studied in five global meta-analyses, while in three of them, most of the studies were originated from China and India (Table 1). Field studies demonstrated a large variability in the response to CR inputs depending on cropping systems, either emission stimulation as for upland crops, or emission reduction and negligible impact as for paddy crops. The C/N ratio of CR was one of the main factors determining the variability of N₂O emission response as demonstrated by two meta-analyses (Chen et al., 2013; Xia et al., 2018). Although the threshold for emission reduction was set at different C/N ratios, namely, >100 and >60, both meta-analyses agreed that cereals straw reduced emissions, while legume and vegetables increased N₂O emissions. Furthermore, CR effects on soil N₂O emissions were highly depended on soil properties, specifically soil moisture content and soil texture (Chen et al., 2013) and clay content (Xia et al., 2018). Although Chen et al. (2013) highlighted the necessity to connect the quantity and quality of CR with soil properties for predicting soil N₂O emissions, in two later meta-analyses, the authors did not consider these moderators (Liu et al., 2014; Fan et al., 2023).

Table 1. Global meta-analyses on the impact of organic matter inputs on N₂O emissions, the main effect sizes, number of independent studies and main moderators studied.

Author	Origin of the most studies	Organic matter type ¹	Study type	Main results	Crops	Effect size (% change from control) ²	Total number of studies (in Europe)	Main moderators
Chen et al. (2013) ³	Global	CR	Laboratory, field	Fig. 2	vegetables, legume, cereals	167% (lab), 47% (field)	28	Soil moisture, texture, C/N ratio of crop residues, amounts of residue C input
Liu et al. (2014) ⁴	China, India	CR	Field	Fig. 2	upland paddy	8.3% -15.2%	11 40	Not studied
Wang et al. (2018) ⁴	Global	CR	Field	Fig. 2	upland paddy	16.6% negligible	14	CR amount
Xia et al. (2018) ³	China	CR	Field	Fig. 3	upland paddy	21.5% -17.3%	–	C/N ratio of crop residues; clay content
Fan et al. (2023) ^{4,5}	China, India	CR	Field	Fig.10	upland and paddy	-8%	18	Not studied
Basche et al. (2014) ⁴	USA	GM	Field	Fig. 4	legume non-legume	490% 7%	26	Type of GM, residue management, measurement period
Muhammad et al. (2019) ⁴	Global	GM	Field	Fig. 2	legume non-legume	61% -36%	41 (13)	quality and quantity of GM, residue management, soil texture
Han et al. (2017) ^{3,5}	Global	GM	Field	Fig. 1	mainly non-legume	-6%	21 (5)	Measurement period

Zhou et al. (2017) ^{4,5}	Global	LM	Field	Fig. 2b	upland and paddy	46.9%	36 (7)	Clay content, soil pH, soil texture
Han et al. (2017) ^{3,5}	Global	LM, SL	Field	Fig. 1	mainly maize and wheat	<i>12%</i>	23 (9)	Clay content
Wei et al. (2020) ^{4,5}	Global	mainly LM, SL	Field	Fig. 2b	maize	<i>-12.7%</i>	n.d.	OM amount, study duration, replacement rate of chemical fertilizer with OM
Fan et al. (2023) ^{4,5}	China, India	LM	Field	Fig. 9a	upland and paddy	<i>-15.3%</i>	45	Not studied
Zhou et al. (2017) ^{4,5}	Global	COM, DI	Field	Fig. 2b	upland and paddy	2.8%	12 (3)	Clay content, soil pH, soil texture
Kong et al. (2023) ^{4,5}	Global	DI	Field, greenhouse	Fig. 2a	upland and paddy	negligible	n.d.	Replacement rate of chemical fertilizer with DI
Cayuela et al. (2014) ⁴	–	BIO	Mostly laboratory and greenhouse	Fig. 1	–	-54%	30	Soil pH, soil texture, BIO amount
Verhoeven et al. (2017) ⁴	Global	BIO	Field	Fig. 2	upland paddy	-11.5% -14%	43 (6)	BIO amount, BIO pH, field site, measurement period
Liu et al. (2018) ⁴	Global	BIO	Laboratory, greenhouse, field	Fig. 5c	various	-32%	70	Soil texture, BIO amount
Borchard et al. (2019) ⁴	Global	BIO	Laboratory, field	Fig. 1	cereals, maize, rice, vegetables, perennials, and others	-38%	10	Pedo-climatic characteristics, BIO properties

¹GM, green manure; CR, crop residues; LM, livestock manure; SL, slurry; DI, digestate; BIO, biochar; COM, compost.

²Italic indicates statistically non-significant effect.

³Unweighted meta-analysis. Weighting by sample size is considered as unweighted.

⁴Weighted meta-analysis by the inverse of variance (Hedges et al., 1999).

⁵OM inputs were compared to mineral fertilizers.

n.d., not define

1.2. Cover crop/green manure

Green manure (GM) is a term used to describe crops that are grown and incorporated into the soil to improve its fertility and organic matter content. GM implementation can have different impacts on N₂O emissions depending on the type of crop, the method of incorporation, and the rate of mineral-N fertilization. Legume crops, such as clover or alfalfa, tend to increase N₂O emissions compared to non-legume crops, such as grass or rye, because they fix more N from the atmosphere and release it into the soil (Carter et al., 2014). Composting GM with straw before soil application can reduce N₂O emissions compared to ensiling or fresh incorporation, because composting reduces the N availability and increases the carbon to nitrogen (C/N) ratio of the organic matter. Incorporating GM by ploughing can increase N₂O emissions compared to harrowing, because ploughing promotes anaerobic conditions near the decomposing organic matter, which favors denitrification (Carter et al., 2014). Therefore, GM can have both positive and negative effects on N₂O emissions, depending on how it is managed.

There are three meta-analyses that studied the effect of cover crops/GM on N₂O emissions based on field data (Basche et al., 2014; Han et al., 2017; Muhammad et al., 2019). There was a clear difference between non-legume and legume cover crops in terms of their effect on N₂O emissions: legumes typically resulted in higher N₂O emission, while non-legume cover crops had either a negligible effect or reduced the emission (Table 1). Han et al. (2017) found that with increasing N inputs from cover crops, N₂O emissions were also increasing. There were both environmental and farm management factors that modified the impact of cover crops on N₂O emissions, including fertilizer N rate, precipitation, and the period of measurement (Basche et al., 2014). When measured for time periods of one year or longer, cover crops on average only lead to a small or negligible increase in N₂O emissions. However, incorporation of cover crop residues contributes to an increase in N₂O emissions, while surface-placed residue resulted either in emission reduction or had a negligible effect (Basche et al., 2014; Muhammad et al., 2019).

1.3. Livestock manure, slurry, compost and digestate

Globally, application of animal manure to arable land as organic fertilizer enhances SOC stocks compared to synthetic N fertilizer alone (e.g., Maillard and Angers, 2014). However, the potential of manure application for climate change mitigation by increasing SOC stocks can be attenuated by enhanced N₂O emissions. The magnitude and duration of N₂O emissions from

manure depend on its composition and quality, such as the total N, ammonium-N, organic N, C/N ratio, pH, and water content (Zhou et al., 2017).

The method and timing of manure application can also influence N₂O emissions. For example, surface application or incorporation of manure can reduce N₂O emissions compared to injection or band spreading, because it reduces anaerobic conditions and denitrification potential in the soil (Thorman et al., 2020). Applying manure in spring or summer can also reduce N₂O emissions compared to autumn, because it matches better with crop N demand and reduces N losses (Thorman et al., 2020).

Three global meta-analyses (Han et al., 2017; Zhou et al., 2017; Wei et al., 2020) summarized the effects of manure on N₂O emissions in comparison with mineral fertilizers in the fields, and one meta-analysis included mostly studies in China and India (Fan et al., 2023). Zhou et al. (2017) showed that the application of raw manure significantly increased soil N₂O emissions by an average of 46.9%, however, with increasing soil clay content and pH, effect sizes of manure application on N₂O emissions were decreasing. Three other meta-analyses demonstrated overall small and non-significant effects of manure that varied from -15.3% to 12% (Han et al. 2017; Wei et al., 2020; Fan et al., 2023), but also showed a negative correlation between clay content and the effect sizes (Han et al., 2017). In coarser soils, manure slightly increased N₂O emissions compared to mineral fertilizer, while in finer soils, manure tended to have similar or lower N₂O emission compared to mineral fertilizer (Han et al., 2017). Replacement rate of mineral fertilizer with organic fertilizer was another crucial factor, explaining the variability in effect sizes. Full substitution of mineral fertilizer with organic fertilizer decreased N₂O emission by 25% (Wei et al., 2020).

Two meta-analyses studied the impact of compost and digestate on N₂O emissions that showed small and statistically not significant effects (Zhou et al., 2017; Kong et al., 2023). The effect sizes of N₂O emissions depended on the replacement ratio, and full substitution of mineral fertilizer with digested slurry increased N₂O emissions by 26% (Kong et al., 2023).

1.4. Biochar

Biochar is the solid product remaining from the heating of biomass under oxygen depleted conditions and is intended for use in soil or other environmental applications (Lehmann and Joseph, 2015). Biochar has received immense research attention in the last 15 years to investigate its potential efficacy as a solution to climate change (Smith, 2016; Woolf et al.,

2010), soil and water pollution remediation (Ahmad et al., 2014), and improving agronomic productivity of soils (Jeffery et al., 2017). Its unique feature in a climate mitigation context is that biochar is more resistant to microbial decomposition compared to the biomass feedstock it was made from and thus persists longer in the soil as a carbon store (Lehmann et al., 2015). Conversion of biomass to biochar and its deposition in soil can sequester ~50% of the biomass-C. This is much higher than when crop residues are burnt in the field (~ 3%) or via biological degradation of biomass (<10-25% after 5-10 years) (Lehmann et al., 2006).

Four global meta-analyses synthesized the effect of biochar on N₂O emissions in laboratory, greenhouse, and field experiments with various crops (Cayuela et al., 2014; Verhoeven et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2018; Borchard et al., 2019). Cayuela et al. (2014) included studies conducted mainly in laboratories and greenhouses and demonstrated the largest overall reduction in N₂O emissions by about 50% (Table 1). The biochar feedstock, pyrolysis conditions and C/N ratio were shown to be key factors influencing emissions of N₂O, while a direct correlation was found between the biochar application rate and N₂O emission reductions. Indeed, Liu et al. (2018) demonstrated that along with the biochar addition rate, the magnitude of the reduction in soil N₂O emissions increased, reaching the maximum when biochar addition rate was higher than 40 t ha⁻¹. Interactions between soil texture and biochar and the chemical form of N fertilizer applied with biochar were also found to have a major influence on soil N₂O emissions.

Other global meta-analysis by Verhoeven et al. (2017) showed much lower reductions of N₂O emission due to biochar under field condition (Table 1), and there was a trend of reduced N₂O mitigation in longer-term studies. This meta-analysis consisted of 40 studies from which only 6 studies were conducted in Europe. Liu et al. (2018) showed intermediate effects of biochar addition to soils resulting in a reduction of N₂O emissions by 32%. The authors pointed out that the effect of biochar was largest in loam soils, but small and non-significant for soils with low organic carbon content (≤ 5 g kg⁻¹). Biochar made from manure or pyrolyzed at temperatures lower than 350 °C showed a weak and insignificant reduction of soil N₂O emissions.

Borchard et al (2019) also stressed that although the overall effect of biochar was statistically significant (-38%), N₂O emission reductions tended to be negligible after one year. The use of biochar reduced N₂O emissions in arable farming and horticulture, but not in grassland or perennial crops.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Studies collection

The research question was structured according to the PICO framework (population, intervention, comparator, and outcome):

Population: European arable land;

Intervention: Organic matter inputs (GM, green manure; CR, crop residues; LM, livestock manure; SL, slurry; DI, digestate; BIO, biochar; COM, compost);

Comparator: Inorganic N fertilizers;

Outcome: Cumulative N₂O emissions for a period.

We found the articles by searching for keywords “soil*” AND (“agr*” OR “farm*” OR “field”) AND “Europe” OR Name of European country) AND (“crop residue*” OR “cover crop*” OR “green manure” OR “livestock manure” OR “slurry” OR “compost” OR “biochar” OR “digestate”) AND (“N₂O” OR “nitrous oxide”), using Web of Science, Scopus, Agricola (USDA National Agricultural Library), ScienceDirect, AGRIS-International System for Agricultural System and Technology, and Google Scholar. The outcome from the first search was a large number of studies, which was later refined by selecting European Research organizations with the assumption that only European Research Organizations have the ability to conduct field experiments in Europe. At least one (co-)author needed to be affiliated with these institutes.

The screening was conducted in two stages:

1. The title of each study was examined for relevance. If at this stage it did not indicate the presence of exclusion criteria (Table 2), the abstract was screened.
2. All studies, which passed the abstract screening, were checked for suitability in form of a full text screening.

We also screened the references of global N₂O meta-analyses and reviews on the effect of biochar (Cayuela et al. 2014; Verhoeven et al. 2017; Borchard et al. 2019), crop residues (Chen et al., 2013; Xia et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018), green manure, cover crops (Basche et al., 2014; Abdalla et al., 2019; Muhammad et al., 2019, 2021), manure (Zhou et al., 2017; Sandén et al., 2018; Shakoob et al., 2021), compost, slurry (Sandén et al., 2018), and their databases, if available. Article search was completed in November 2022.

2.2. Inclusion criteria

To be included in the database, a study had to meet the inclusion criteria listed in Table 2. About 200 screened articles contained exclusion criteria, among which the most common laboratory studies and zero N fertilization.

Table 2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria for the literature screening process

Criteria	Inclusion	Exclusion
Language	English	Other than English language
Study location	Europe, including non-EU, and part of Turkey	Other regions of the world
Soil	Mineral	Organic
Study type	Field study	Laboratory, greenhouse, modelling studies (unless primary data from field studies presented as well)
Land use	Arable land	Permanent crops (vineyard; fruit trees; berry plantation; olive grove); Pastures, Rice field; Forests and semi-natural areas; Wetlands
Cropping system	Monoculture, crop rotation, intercropping	Agroforestry
Control 1 (except for crop residues studies)	No OM inputs, no animal- or fish-based organic fertilizer, no other organic amendments (sphagnum peat, wood chips, grass clippings, biosolids, sawdust and wood ash). Doses of mineral N fertilization within the range used in EU. Conventional tillage (up to 30 cm soil depth) crop residues incorporated or removed.	Any OM inputs, animal- or fish-based organic fertilizer organic amendments (sphagnum peat, wood chips, grass clippings, biosolids, sawdust and wood ash). Doses of mineral N fertilization higher or lower than used in EU zero N fertilization. Conventional tillage deeper than 30 cm soil depth, minimum or no-tillage
Control 2 (for CR studies only)	as control 1, but crop residues removed	crop residues incorporated
Treatment	OM inputs (CR, GM, LM, SL, DI, BIO, COM ¹) applied either solely or in combination with inorganic N fertilizers. Conventional tillage, minimum or no-tillage crop residues incorporated to soil or retained on soil surface.	Other OM inputs, not in the list
Means	Reported cumulative N ₂ O emissions for a period for treatment and control in text, tables and figures, or means can be calculated	Not reported and cannot be calculated, or results expressed as a daily flux
Standard deviation or standard error	Reported for treatment and control or can be calculated from statistics by using EX-TRACT tool (Acutis et. al., 2021, 2022)	Not reported and cannot be calculated by using EX-TRACT tool (non-available statistics or experimental design)
Sample size (number of replicates)	Reported in tables, figures, or methods	Not reported

¹ GM, green manure; CR, crop residues; LM, livestock manure; SL, slurry; DI, digestate; BIO, biochar; COM, compost

2.3. Data extraction

The data extraction method is crucial to deal with the non-independence of the observations that can lead to underestimations of the standard error of the mean effect and therefore liberal evaluations of the statistical significance of effects (Gurevitch and Hedges, 1999; Nakagawa et al., 2017).

To avoid problems with non-independence of the effect sizes, only one pair comparison corresponding to the longest period of N₂O measurements was extracted from a study. If an article reported results for several OM inputs, a treatment was randomly selected, taking care that the number of studies for each OM type was comparable. If an article reported results from different experimental sites with different pedo-climatic characteristics, or from the same site, but with different soil characteristics, those sites were considered as independent studies and were included in the database. However, if several articles referred to the same experimental site with the same pedological characteristics, the article with the longest experimental duration was selected.

Data were extracted from tables and digitized from figures using the ImageJ 1.37 program (Schneider et al., 2012). Standard errors (SE) were converted to standard deviations (SD) where necessary ($SD = SE * \sqrt{n}$, where n is the number of replicates). When no measure of variability was provided, we extracted the SD from the ANOVA table using the EX-TRACT tool (Acutis et al., 2021; Acutis et al., 2022). This tool allows the estimation of the experimental error (i.e., standard deviation and standard error of treatments mean) associated to statistical analysis results of published articles (i.e., estimated from the LSD, P(F) values or even from the letters assignment indicating differences among means based on the results of a multiple comparison test).

2.4. Database creation

We collected forty-six articles published between 1993 and 2022 in peer-reviewed scientific journals, as well as a project report, and a PhD thesis (Table 3; Appendix). The database consists of 53 field studies, located in 46 sites on loam soils, mostly, across 15 European countries covering all European climate zones, from Alpine North to Mediterranean South (Table 3, Figure 1). Three studies on the effect of CR (Nett et al., 2016; Essich et al., 2020; Rittl et al. 2022) were not included in the database due to extremely large effect sizes ($\ln R = 1.8 - 2.05$, or 500 – 680%), which violate the normal distribution of effect sizes. The entire

database for meta-analysis will be available in Zenodo when the results of the meta-analysis are published in a peer-reviewed scientific journal.

All calculated cumulative N₂O emissions were estimated from chamber measurements in the fields during periods from 30 up to 1070 days, throughout the growing season (31 studies), outside growing season (3 studies) or during all year (19 studies). Types of OM inputs included 10 studies on CR, 10 on SL, 9 on GM, 8 on BIO, 7 on DI, 6 on COM and 3 on LM. Total N supply due to OM inputs ranged between 20 to 418 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, and C/N ratio ranged between 2.7 and 390. In 32 field studies, organic matters were added into soils in combination with inorganic N fertilizers, resulting in total N amounts more than in the control (26 studies), equal to the control (5 studies), or less (one study). In the other studies, OM inputs were applied solely at the N amounts either more than in control (9 studies), equal to the control (7 studies), or less (4 studies), or unknown amount (1 study).

Altogether 13 studies were conducted in Spain, 11 in Germany, 4 in Italy, 3 in Denmark, England, Finland, France, and Norway, 2 in Scotland, Switzerland, and the Netherlands, and one in Greece, Cyprus, Slovakia and Sweden. Annual precipitation and average annual temperature varied between 250 mm and 1300 mm, and between 4.5 °C and 19.6 °C, respectively. Diverse arable crops, mainly cereals (maize, spring wheat, winter wheat, spring barley), were cultivated in monoculture or in crop rotations in conventional (47 studies) or organic (6 studies) farming system in the treatment plots (control plots were always conventional).

The soil management of the treatments included conventional tillage in 43 studies, minimum tillage in 4 studies and no-tillage in one study, while five studies did not report soil tillage management. No cover crops were used in 41 studies, non-legume cover crops in 9 studies, and legume in 3 studies. Fields were not irrigated in 37 studies, while irrigated in 16 studies.

Figure 1. The location of 46 experimental sites used for meta-analysis and related Environmental zones of Europe (source: Metzger et al., 2005). ALN-Alpine North; ALS-Alpine South; ANA- Anatolian; ATC- Atlantic Central; ATN- Alpine North; BOR- Boreal; CON-Continental; LUS- Lusitanian; MDM- Mediterranean Mountains; MDN- Mediterranean North; MDS- Mediterranean South; NEM- Nemoral; PAN- Pannonian.

Table 3. Studies included in the meta-analysis of field experiments on the effect of organic matter inputs on N₂O emissions in European arable land.

ID	Authors ¹	Country	Site	Soil texture ²	Environmental zone ³	OM type ⁴
1	Abalos et al. (2013)	Spain	El Encín	SCL	MDS	CR
2	Alluvione et al. (2010)	Italy	Turin	SiL	MDM	GM
3	Autret et al. (2019)	France	La Cage	SiL	ATC	GM
4	Baggs et al. (2000)	Scotland	Mosstowie	SL	ATN	CR
5	Baral et al. (2017)	Denmark	Foulumgaard	LS	ATN	SL
6	Bosco et al. (2019)	Italy	Pisa	LS	MDN	GM
7	Calleja-Cervantes et al. (2017)	Spain	Arazuri	SiCL	LUS	DI
8-1	Dambreville et al. (2008)	France	Champ Noël	SiL	ATC	SL
8-2	Dambreville et al. (2008)	France	Le Rheu	SiL	ATC	LM
9	Dicke et al. (2015)	Germany	Berge	SL	ATN	DI
10	Franco-Luesma et al. (2022)	Spain	Aula Dei	SiL	MDS	GM
11	Guardia et al. (2017)	Spain	El Encín	SCL	MDS	COM
12	Hagemann et al. (2017)	Germany	Goldener Acker	SiCL	ATC	BIO
13	Hansen et al. (1993)	Norway	Surnadal	SL	ALN	SL
14	Herr et al. (2019)	Germany	Heidfeldhof	SiL	ATN	SL
15	Horák et al. (2017)	Slovakia	Malanta	L	PAN	BIO
16	Hüppi et al. (2015)	Switzerland	Zurich	CL	CON	BIO
17	Kesenheimer et al. (2019)	Germany	Ihinger Hof	SiL	ATN	CR
18	Köbke et al. (2022)	Germany	Reinshof	SiL	ATN	CR
19	Kontopoulou et al. (2015)	Greece	Agrinio	CL	MDS	COM
20	Lagomarsino et al. (2022)	Italy	Cascina Baroncina	SL	MDN	DI
21	Louro et al. (2015)	Spain	Mabegondo	SiL	LUS	SL
22	Ludwig et al. (2011)	Germany	Darmstadt	LS	PAN	LM
23	Maris et al. (2018)	Spain	Almacelles	CL	MDS	CR
24	Mateo-Marín et al. (2020)	Spain	Soto Lezcano	SiL	MDS	SL
25	Meijide et al. (2007)	Spain	La Poveda	SL	MDS	COM
26	Meijide et al. (2009)	Spain	El Encín	SCL	MDS	COM
27	Nadeem et al. (2012)	Norway	Østrevoll	SiCL	NEM	DI
28	O'Toole (2021)	Norway	NMBU field station	SiCL	BOR	BIO
29	Olofsson and Ernfors (2022)	Sweden	Lönnstorp	L	CON	GM
30	Omirou et al. (2020)	Cyprus	Acheleia Paphos	C	MDS	COM
31	Perälä et al. (2006)	Finland	Vihti	C	BOR	SL
32	Plaza-Bonilla et al. (2014)	Spain	Northeastern Spain	SiCL	MDN	SL
33-1	Regina et al. (2021)	Finland	Jokioinen	LS	BOR	GM
33-2	Regina et al. (2021)	Finland	Jokioinen	S	BOR	GM
34	Rothardt et al. (2021)	Germany	Hohenschulen	SCL	ATN	CR
35	Sanchez-Martin et al. (2010)	Spain	El Encín	SCL	MDS	LM

36	Sánchez-García et al. (2020)	Spain	Campus of Espinardo	SL	MDS	BIO
37	Sanz-Cobena et al. (2014)	Spain	la Chimenea	SiCL	MDS	GM
38	Sarkodie-Addo et al. (2003)	England	Wye	SiL	ATC	GM
39	Scotti et al. (2022)	Italy	Cascina Baroncina	SL	MDN	BIO
40-1	Senbayram et al. (2014)	Germany	Karkendamm	S	ATN	DI
40-2	Senbayram et al. (2014)	Germany	Hohenschulen	SL	ATN	DI
41	Skinner et al. (2019)	Switzerland	Therwil	SiL	ATC	COM
42	Sun et al. (2017)	Germany	Berge	SL	CON	BIO
43-1	Sylvester-Bradley et al.(2015)	England	Gleadthorpe	SL	ATC	CR
43-2	Sylvester-Bradley et al. (2015)	Scotland	Edinburgh	CL	ATN	CR
43-3	Sylvester-Bradley et al. (2015)	England	Terrington	CL	ATN	CR
44	Taghizadeh-Toosi et al. (2022)	Denmark	Foulum	LS	ATN	CR
45	Thers et al. (2020)	Denmark	Askov Experimental Station	SL	ATN	BIO
46	van Groenigen et al. (2004)	the Netherlands	Leeuwarden	SiCL	ATC	SL
47	Velthof and Mosquera (2011)	the Netherlands	Wageningen	S	ATC	SL
48	Wolf et al. (2014)	Germany	Braunschweig	SL	ATN	DI

¹ Reference list of articles appears in Appendix.

² C, Clay; CL, Clay loam; L, Loam; LS, Loamy sand; S, Sand ; SCL, Sandy clay loam; SL, Sandy loam; Si, Silt; SiL, Silt loam; SiCL, Silty clay loam.

³ALN, Alpine North; ATC, Atlantic Central; ATN, Alpine North; BOR, Boreal; CON, Continental; LUS, Lusitanian; MDM, Mediterranean Mountains; MDN, Mediterranean North MDS, Mediterranean South; NEM, Nemoral; PAN, Pannonian.

⁴ GM, green manure; CR, crop residues; LM, livestock manure; SL, slurry; DI, digestate; BIO, biochar; COM, compost

2.5. Explanatory variables (moderators)

To explain the variation in the N₂O changes due to OM inputs, we included 20 explanatory variables derived from the database and grouped them into 5 categories, namely, study characteristics, OM input characteristics, climate, soil and agronomic management (Table 4). Tillage practices were not included in the list of explanatory variables, since fields were conventionally tilled in majority studies, and there were lack of studies with minimum tillage or no-till.

Spearman rank order correlation (r_s) was run between soil characteristics and climate to assess their intercorrelation.

Table 4. Categorical and continuous explanatory variables (moderators) included in the meta-analysis.

Variable category	Explanatory variables	Group or range
Study characteristics	Measurement period (days)	30 – 1069
	Season of N ₂ O measurements	All year, in growing season, outside of growing season
OM input characteristics	Type	CR, GM, LM, SL, DI, COM, BIO ¹
	OM input strategy	Replacement (inorganic N fertilizer replacement); addition (addition in combination with inorganic N fertilizer)
	C/N ratio	2.7 – 390
Climate	Total N supply in OM (kg ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	20 – 418
	Environmental zone	ALN, ATC, ATN, BOR, CON, LUS, MDM, MDN, MDS, NEM, PAN ²
	Annual precipitation (mm)	275 – 1300
Soil	Average annual temperature (°C)	4.5 – 19.6
	SOC (%)	0.69 – 4.5
	Clay (%)	1 – 52
	Sand (%)	2 – 91
	Soil C/N ratio	7 – 21
	pH	4.8 – 8.4
Agronomic management	Soil texture	C, CL, L, LS, S, SCL, SL, Si, SiL, SiCL ³
	Total N supply as sum of inorganic N and OM (kg ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	25 – 613
	Farming system	Conventional, organic
	Cropping system	Monoculture, crop rotation, intercropping
	Cover crops	Non-legume, legume, no cover crops
	Irrigation	Irrigation, no irrigation

¹GM, green manure; CR, crop residues; LM, livestock manure; SL, slurry; DI, digestate; BIO, biochar; COM, compost

²ALN, Alpine North; ATC, Atlantic Central; ATN, Alpine North; BOR, Boreal; CON, Continental; LUS, Lusitanian; MDM, Mediterranean Mountains; MDN, Mediterranean North; MDS, Mediterranean South; NEM, Nemoral; PAN, Pannonian.

³C, Clay; CL, Clay loam; L, Loam; LS, Loamy sand; S, Sand (unspecified); SCL, Sandy clay loam; SL, Sandy loam; Si, Silt; SiL, Silt loam; SiCL, Silty clay loam.

2.6. Meta-analysis

Meta-analyses were conducted using Meta Win 2.0 statistical software (Rosenberg et al., 2000) and IBM SPSS Statistics 29.

Quantitative meta-analysis involves calculating an effect size (i.e., the magnitude of the treatment effect) that can be averaged across independent studies. Since two experimental groups have been compared, the response ratio (R) was computed for the response variables as an index of the effect size:

$$R = \bar{X}_{OM}/\bar{X}_C \quad [1]$$

where \bar{X}_{OM} and \bar{X}_C represent the means for treatments (solely OM input or in combination with inorganic N fertilizers) and for control (inorganic N fertilizers), respectively, averaged for experimental replicates.

Since the distribution of R is skewed, performing statistical analyses in the metric of the natural logarithm of R is usually preferred due to its much more normal distribution in small samples than that of R (Hedges et al., 1999):

$$\ln(R) = \ln(\bar{X}_{OM}/\bar{X}_C) = \ln(\bar{X}_{OM}) - \ln(\bar{X}_C) \quad [2]$$

A normal distribution for $\ln R$ was tested by Shapiro-Wilk test.

We calculated the variance of $\ln(R)$ as:

$$V_{\ln(R)} = \frac{(SD_{OM})^2}{n_{OM}(\bar{X}_{OM})^2} + \frac{(SD_C)^2}{n_C(\bar{X}_C)^2} \quad [3]$$

where SD_{OM} and SD_C are the corresponding standard deviations, and n is the sample size (number of replicates).

We assumed that studies do not share the same effect sizes and consequently we used a random effects model to combine estimates across the studies. The application of this kind of model accounts for experimental method differences between studies (that are considered only a random sample of possible effect sizes) which may introduce variability (“heterogeneity”, τ^2) among the true effects.

We calculated the weighted mean of the log response ratio for all studies as:

$$\overline{\ln(R)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i \ln R_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i} \quad [4]$$

where $\ln R_i$ is the log response ratio for study i , n is the number of studies, and w_i is the weight for study i , defined as (Borenstein et al., 2009):

$$w_i = \frac{1}{V_i + \tau^2} \quad [5]$$

where V_i is the variance of the study i and τ^2 denotes the amount of residual heterogeneity (between-study variance). Because the variance of the effect sizes is a function of the sample size (Eq. 3), studies with a larger sample size had lower variances and received heavier weights.

The τ^2 parameter is considered the variance of the true effect size. Since it is not possible to compute it from the entire population of the effect size, the τ^2 is an estimation from the observed effect by using DerSimonian and Laird method:

$$\tau^2 = \frac{(Q - df)}{C} \quad [6]$$

where

$$Q = \sum_{i=1}^k w_i (Y_i - M)^2; \quad df = n - 1; \quad C = \sum w_i - \frac{\sum w_i^2}{\sum w_i}$$

where w_i is the study weight, Y_i is the study effect size, M is the summary effect, and n is the number of studies.

A random effects model served to combine estimates across the studies, assuming that studies in each subgroup do not share the same effect size. We used a bootstrap statistical method (Efron and Tibshirani, 1986) to generate bias-corrected 95% CIs around the log response ratios from 4999 iterations. To test whether $\ln R$ differed between the groups of categorical explanatory variables, we used the χ^2 test to examine the between-group heterogeneity (Q_B). To study the effect of continuous explanatory variables, we ran weighted meta-regressions with $\ln R$ as the dependent variable and the continuous variables as independent ones. We also used the χ^2 test to examine the model heterogeneity (Q_M), which describes the amount of heterogeneity explained by the regression models.

For the outliers' identification, we used the backward search algorithm specifically developed for meta-analysis (Mavridis et al., 2017). Backward search algorithms start with the full data

set and remove sequentially outlying observations until all outliers have been removed. This method can be useful when there are a few outlying studies (Mavridis et al., 2017).

Results were back-transformed, except for meta-regression, and reported in the text and figures as percentage changes from the controls:

$$N_2O \text{ emission change (\%)} = [EXP(\ln(R)) - 1] * 100\% \quad [7]$$

The OM input effects on the N₂O emissions were considered significantly different from the controls if the 95% CIs did not overlap with zero.

2.7. Sensitivity analysis

Funnel plot asymmetry, which may indicate publication bias in meta-analysis, was examined by plotting $\ln R$ against its SE (Sterne and Egger, 2001). Moreover, the Eggers's regression-based test was conducted enabling the detection of funnel plot asymmetry. A statistically non-significant p -value of the Egger's test indicates no publication bias.

For estimating the magnitude of the file-drawer problem a fail-safe number (Nfs) was calculated. A fail-safe number is the number of non-significant, unpublished, or missing studies need to be added to a meta-analysis to change its results from significant to non-significant. Specifically, we used the Rosenthal's method that estimates how many missing studies we would need to retrieve and incorporate in the analysis before the p -value became non-significant (Borenstein et al., 2009).

Trim-and-fill analysis was performed to allow one to enter values for "missing" studies to generate a symmetric funnel plot from which a new mean effect size can be estimated (Koricheva et al., 2013).

3. Results

3.1. Overall effect

The effect sizes for 53 studies examining the effect of OM inputs on N₂O emissions were normally distributed (W-Statistic = 0.984, $p = 0.697$; Figure 2). The forest plot indicates the large variability of effect sizes, ranging from -75% ($\ln R = -1.35$) to +200% ($\ln R = 1.10$) (Figure 3). The overall effect across all studies had a slight tendency to emission reduction by 10% ($\ln R = -0.12$) compared to inorganic N fertilizers (control). Since the CI (-20%; 0%) overlapped with zero (the control), this indicates that the overall effect of OM inputs on N₂O emission was

not statistically significant. The effect related neither to the measurement period (covered the period from one month to three years) nor to the season of N₂O measurement (Table 5).

Figure 2. The distribution of effect sizes for 53 studies examining the effect of organic matter inputs on N₂O emissions. The dashed line indicates inorganic N fertilizers (control).

Figure 3. Forest plot showing effect sizes for 53 independent studies examining the effect of organic matter inputs on N₂O emissions compared to inorganic N fertilizers (control). Black squares are summary effect estimates for each study with lower and upper 95% CIs. Square size corresponds to study weight. The white square indicates weighted average with 95% CIs across all studies. The dashed vertical line indicates inorganic N fertilizers (control).

3.2. Effect of OM input characteristics

There was a statistically significant positive relationship between the C/N ratio of OM inputs and the emission reduction (Figure 4; Table 5). According to the meta-regression analysis, OM with C/N ratio < 20 had a risk for increased N₂O emissions, while OM with C/N ratio of 50 reduced N₂O by about 10%, and with C/N ratio of 100 reduced N₂O by 25%. Organic matter inputs with the largest C/N ratio, such as biochar, may have a potential to reduce the emission up to 65% (ln R = -1.01). Sub-group analysis showed that seven studied OM types had somehow different effect ($p = 0.056$; Table 5).

Figure 4. The relationship between C/N ratio of organic matter inputs and N₂O emission change compared to inorganic N fertilizers (control). GM, green manure; CR, crop residues; LM, livestock manure; SL, slurry; DI, digestate; BIO, biochar; COM, compost. The symbol size represents the study weight. The dashed line indicates inorganic N fertilizers (control). Crosses indicate the outliers (ID38, ID39, ID40-1) and n , number of independent studies. Statistics for meta-regression appears in Table 5. For back-transformation of $\ln R$, see Equation (7).

Table 5. A weighted linear regression analysis (Q_M) and subgroup analysis (Q_B) for the effects of study characteristics and OM input characteristics on the effect size ($\ln R$).

Variable category	Explanatory variables	OM group ¹	Q -test	df between,	p	Figure		
				total				
Study characteristics	Measurement period	1&2	Q_M	0.34	1,52	ns	–	
	Season of N ₂ O measurements	1&2	Q_B	4.2	2,52	ns	–	
OM input characteristics	C/N ratio	1&2	Q_M	11.2	1,35	<0.001	Fig. 4 ²	
	Type	1&2	Q_B	12.3	6,52	0.056	Fig. 5a	
	OM ₁ vs. OM ₂	–	Q_B	10.5	1,52	0.001	Fig. 5b	
	Input strategy	Total N supply in OM	1	Q_B	5.5	1,38	0.019	Fig. 5b
			2	Q_B	0.0	1,13	ns	Fig. 5b
		1	Q_M	1.98	1,37	ns	–	
		2	Q_M	0.82	1,13	ns	–	

¹OM₁=GM, green manure; CR, crop residues; LM, livestock manure; SL, slurry; DI, digestate; OM₂=BIO, biochar; COM, compost

²Outliers: ID38 Sarkodie-Addo et al. (2003); ID39 Scotti et al. (2022); ID40-1 Senbayram et al. (2014)

ns, statistically non-significant

The effect of OM types, such as GM, CR, LM, SL, DI, varied from -18% to +15%, and their CIs overlapped with zero, indicating non-significant effects (Figure 5a). In contrast, COM and BIO significantly reduced N₂O emissions by 33% (95%CI: -36% to -18%, $n = 6$) and 25% (95%CI: -36% to -18%, $n = 8$), respectively, compared to inorganic N fertilizers (Figure 5a).

To obtain enough studies for moderator analysis, and due to clear variability in the effect sizes between BIO and COM, when compared to other OM types, the database was merged into two larger groups, namely OM₁ (GM, CR, LM, SL and DI) and OM₂ (BIO and COM). The difference between them was statistically significant ($p = 0.001$; Figure 5b; Table 5). The OM₁ group showed no effect on N₂O emissions (0%; CI -14%, 15%, $n = 39$). However, the input strategy was crucial, since the OM₁ addition to soils in combination with inorganic N fertilizers tended to increase emissions by 14% (95%CI: -3% to 41%, $n = 22$), while N fertilizer replacement by OM₁ showed a decline in N₂O by 16% (95%CI: -35% to 2%, $n = 17$). It should be noted that CR were added into soils in combination with inorganic N fertilizer, but there was no inorganic N fertilizer replacement with CR. When the CR experiments ($n = 10$) were excluded from the previous sub-group analysis, the difference between the input strategies for GM, LM, SL and DI became highly significant ($Q_B=7.4$, $df=1,28$; $p= 0.007$, $n = 29$), and their addition increased N₂O by 30% (95%CI: 2% to 74%, $n = 12$) compared to control.

In contrast, OM₂ reduced N₂O emission statistically significantly by 30%, (95%CI: CI -40% to -18%, $n = 14$) regardless of the input strategy. Finally, the total N supply in OM, ranging from 20 – 418 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, was not a relevant factor for both groups (Table 5).

Figure 5. N₂O emission change due to organic matter types (GM, green manure; CR, crop residues; LM, livestock manure; SL, slurry; DI, digestate; BIO, biochar; COM, compost) (a) individually, (b) clustered to the larger groups (OM₁; OM₂) and separated by OM input strategy (Rep, replacement; Add, addition). Filled circles indicate GM, CR, LM, SL, DI (OM₁), open circles indicate BIO, COM (OM₂). Square corresponds to overall effect. The dashed vertical line indicates inorganic N fertilizers (control). Numbers in parentheses indicate the number of independent studies. N₂O emission changes were considered significantly different from the controls if the 95% CIs did not overlap with zero. Asterisks indicate p-value of the between-group heterogeneity test (Q_B). * $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.001$. Statistics for subgroup analysis appear in Table 5.

3.3. Effect of pedo-climatic factors

The meta-regressions indicated no relationships between climatic characteristics and N₂O emission change due to OM₁ inputs (Figure 6a, b; Table 6), suggesting equal applicability of results of meta-analysis to all European environmental zones. In contrast, for BIO and COM, annual average temperature and annual precipitation were important factors governing the N₂O

emission reduction, with a smaller effect under warmer or drier climatic conditions, such as Mediterranean South, than that in temperate or boreal climate (Figure 6c, d; Table 6). For example, increasing annual average temperature from 5°C (boreal) to 15°C (Mediterranean South) reduced the efficiency of BIO and COM to mitigate N₂O from 55% to 23%. With a further temperature increase to 20°C, the efficiency of BIO and COM to reduce N₂O emission dropped to zero.

Table 6. A weighted linear meta-regression analysis (Q_M) and subgroup analysis (Q_B) for the effects of pedo-climatic factors on the effect size ($\ln R$).

Variable category	Explanatory variables	OM group ¹	Q_M	Q -test	$df_{\text{between, total}}$	p	Figure
Climate	Annual average temperature	1	Q_M	2.0	1,38	ns	Fig. 6a
		2	Q_M	10.1	1,12	0.002	Fig. 6c ²
	Annual precipitation	1	Q_M	0.57	1,38	ns	Fig. 6b
		2	Q_M	7.7	1,13	0.005	Fig. 6d
	Environmental zones	1	Q_B	10.3	5,33	ns	–
		2	Q_B	13.4	2,9	0.001	–
Soil	Soil pH	1	Q_M	0.59	1,35	ns	–
		2	Q_M	4.0	1,13	0.046	–
	Sand	1	Q_M	0.00	1,38	ns	–
		2	Q_M	15.4	1,13	<0.001	–
	Soil pH x Sand	2	Q_M	22.6	2,13	<0.001	Fig. 7
	Clay	1&2	Q_M	0.92	1,52	ns	–
	SOC	1&2	Q_M	0.20	1,51	ns	–
	Soil C/N ratio	1&2	Q_M	0.23	1,38	ns	–

¹OM₁=GM, green manure; CR, crop residues; LM, livestock manure; SL, slurry; DI, digestate; OM₂=BIO, biochar; COM, compost

²Outlier: ID45 Thers et al. (2020)

ns, statistically non-significant

Grouping the results into soil texture categories for a sub-group analysis yielded a low number of studies per group, therefore, running meta-regressions suited better (than sub-group analysis) to examine the effect of soil characteristics. We found that the contents of sand, clay or SOC, soil pH and soil C/N ratio did not modify the effect size in OM₁ group (Table 6). In contrast, increasing soil pH and sand content, resulted in a decline of the mitigation effect of BIO and COM (Figure 7). Several confounding factors, such as intercorrelation between soil pH and with both annual average temperature ($r_s = 0.781$, $p < 0.001$, $n = 14$) and annual precipitation ($r_s = -0.673$, $p < 0.001$, $n = 14$) should be interpreted with care. For example, studies located in Mediterranean South had alkaline soils, with pH ranging between 7.4 and 8.4, while studies located in temperate and boreal zones had acidic soil, with pH ranging between 5.7 and 6.5. This does not allow us to draw a clear conclusion on which factor, soil pH or climate, is the most important in terms of driving N₂O emission reduction by BIO and COM.

Figure 6. (a, b) Scatter plots between N_2O emission change due to green manure (GM); crop residues (CR); livestock manure (LM); slurry (SL); digestate (DI) and annual average temperature and annual precipitation. (c, d) Weighted meta-regressions (solid lines) between N_2O emission change due to biochar (BIO) and compost (COM) and annual average temperature and annual precipitation. The symbol size represents the study weight. The dashed line indicates the inorganic N fertilizers (control), while the cross indicates the outlier (ID45 Thers et al., 2020). Number indicates the number of independent studies. Statistics for meta-regressions appear in Table 6. For back-transformation of $\ln R$, see Equation (7). For abbreviations of environmental zones, see Figure 1.

BIO, COM

Figure 7. Weighted meta-regressions between N₂O emission change due to biochar (BIO) and compost (COM), and combination of soil pH and sand content. The symbol size represents the study weight. The dashed line indicates inorganic N fertilizers (control). Statistics for meta-regression appears in Table 6. For back-transformation of ln *R*, see Equation (7).

3.4. Effect of management practices

There were no relationships between agronomic management practices (total N supply, farming systems, cropping systems, presence of cover crops or irrigation) and the effect sizes (Table 7). This indicates that N₂O emission changes due to OM inputs were independent of the management practices studied here.

Table 7. A weighted linear regression analysis (Q_M) and subgroup analysis (Q_B) for the effects of agronomic management practices on the effect sizes (ln R).

Explanatory variables	OM groups ¹		Q -test	df between, total	p
Total N supply (sum of inorganic N fertilizer and OM)	1&2	Q_M	2.9	1,51	ns
Farming system	1&2	Q_B	0.96	1,52	ns
Cropping system	1&2	Q_B	3.4	2,52	ns
Cover crops	1&2	Q_B	0.46	2,52	ns
Irrigation	1&2	Q_B	0.0	1,51	ns

¹ OM₁=GM, green manure; CR, crop residues; LM, livestock manure; SL, slurry; DI, digestate; OM₂=BIO, biochar; COM, compost
ns, statistically non-significant

3.5. Sensitivity analysis

Funnel plot for N₂O emissions studies showed no asymmetry (Figure 8). In addition, no publication bias was detected by the Eggers's regression-based test ($p = 0.896$; Table 8). The trim-and-fill analysis of publication bias for meta-analysis was also implemented. The imputed five "missing" studies shifted slightly ln R from -0.12 to -0.17 (Figure 8). However, the adjusted estimate is close to the original.

For studies on biochar and compost, a fail-safe number is 77, indicating that the results are robust. It would need to be added a consistent number of unpublished, or missing studies (that is 5.5 times more than in the present meta-analysis), to change the results from significant to non-significant.

Figure 8. Funnel plot for N₂O emissions studies showing original (blue circles) and added “missing” (red circles) effect sizes, when using a random effect model. The red dashed line represents the original estimates of $\ln R$ (-0.12); black solid line represents the revised estimate of $\ln R$ (-0.17), assuming five missing studies.

Table 8. Egger's regression-based test¹ enabling the publication bias.

Parameter	Coefficient	Std. Error	t	<i>p</i>
Intercept	-0.126	0.0826	-1.525	0.133
Standard error of $\ln R$	0.044	0.3357	0.131	0.896

¹Random-effects meta-regression.

4. Conclusion

The results of meta-analysis showed that the effect of OM inputs on N₂O emissions was highly variable, ranging from -75% to +200% compared to inorganic N fertilizers. The summarized effect across all studies ($n = 53$) had a slight tendency to emission reduction by 10%. This effect became more pronounced with increasing C/N ratio of OM inputs, as meta-regression showed.

Among the different OM types, only compost and biochar significantly reduced N₂O emissions by 25% and 33%, respectively. A similar overall effect of biochar was published in the global meta-analysis by Liu et al. (2018). However, with increasing soil pH and sand content, the mitigation effect of biochar and compost was declining. Their effect also depended on climate, with less emission reduction in warmer or drier climatic conditions than in temperate climates. However, due to intercorrelation, it is difficult to confidently conclude, which factor, soil pH or climate, was the most important moderator in terms of driving N₂O emission reduction by biochar and compost.

The effect of other OM types, such as green manure, crop residues, livestock manure, slurry and digestate on N₂O emissions varied from -18% to +15% compared to inorganic N fertilizers. However, their effects were not statistically significant regardless of the different pedo-climatic factors. The results of this European meta-analysis are consistent with the global meta-analyses by Han et al. (2017); Wei et al (2020) and Fan et al. (2023), who demonstrated statistically non-significant effects of OM inputs on N₂O emissions (-15% to +12%, Table 1).

However, the input strategy was crucial, since the OM addition in combination with inorganic N fertilizers tended to increase N₂O emissions, while fertilizer replacement by the OM inputs showed a decline in N₂O emissions. Finally, different agricultural management practices, such as presence of cover crops, irrigation, and different farming and cropping systems did not modify N₂O emission change due to any type of OM inputs compared to the control.

This meta-analysis calls for an increase in the number of European studies, which monitor N₂O emissions in the field with application of several types of OM inputs, particularly, green manure, livestock manure, slurry and digestate since these showed variable results.

5. Appendix. Reference list of articles included in the meta-analysis.

Number corresponds to article ID.

1. Abalos, D., Sanz-Cobena, A., Garcia-Torres, L., Van Groenigen, J.W. & Vallejo, A. (2013). Role of maize stover incorporation on nitrogen oxide emissions in a non-irrigated Mediterranean barley field. *Plant and Soil*, vol. 364, no. 1, 357-371.
2. Alluvione, F., Bertora, C., Zavattaro, L. & Grignani, C. (2010). Nitrous oxide and carbon dioxide emissions following green manure and compost fertilization in corn. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, vol. 74, no. 2, 384-395.
3. Autret, B., Beaudoin, N., Rakotovololona, L., Bertrand, M., Grandeau, G., Gréhan, E., Ferchaud, F. & Mary, B. (2019). Can alternative cropping systems mitigate nitrogen losses and improve GHG balance? Results from a 19-yr experiment in Northern France. *Geoderma*, vol. 342, 20-33.
4. Baggs, E.M., Watson, C.A. & Rees, R.M. (2000). The fate of nitrogen from incorporated cover crop and green manure residues. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems*, vol. 56, no. 2, 153-163.
5. Baral, K.R., Labouriau, R., Olesen, J.E. & Petersen, S.O. (2017). Nitrous oxide emissions and nitrogen use efficiency of manure and digestates applied to spring barley. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, vol. 239, 188-198.
6. Bosco, S., Volpi, I., Antichi, D., Ragaglini, G. & Frascioni, C. (2019). Greenhouse gas emissions from soil cultivated with vegetables in crop rotation under Integrated, organic and organic conservation management in a Mediterranean environment. *Agronomy*, vol. 9, no. 8, 446.
7. Calleja-Cervantes, M.E., Aparicio-Tejo, P.M., Villadas, P.J., Irigoyen, I., Irañeta, J., Fernández-González, A.J., Fernández-López, M. & Menéndez, S. (2017). Rational application of treated sewage sludge with urea increases GHG mitigation opportunities in Mediterranean soils. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, vol. 238, 114-127.
8. Dambreville, C., Morvan, T. & Germon, J. (2008). N₂O emission in maize-crops fertilized with pig slurry, matured pig manure or ammonium nitrate in Brittany. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, vol. 123, no. 1-3, 201-210.
9. Dicke, C., Andert, J., Ammon, C., Kern, J., Meyer-Aurich, A. & Kaupenjohann, M. (2015) Effects of different biochars and digestate on N₂O fluxes under field conditions. *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 524, 310-318.
10. Franco-Luesma, S., Lafuente, V., Alonso-Ayuso, M., Bielsa, A., Kouchami-Sardoo, I., Arrúe, J.L. & Álvaro-Fuentes, J. (2022). Maize diversification and nitrogen fertilization effects on soil nitrous oxide emissions in irrigated Mediterranean conditions. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 1214.
11. Guardia, G., Cangani, M.T., Sanz-Cobena, A., Junior, J.L. & Vallejo, A. (2017). Management of pig manure to mitigate NO and yield-scaled N₂O emissions in an irrigated Mediterranean crop. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, vol. 238, 55-66.

12. Hagemann, N., Harter, J., Kaldamukova, R., Guzman-Bustamante, I., Ruser, R., Graeff, S., Kappler, A. & Behrens, S. (2017). Does soil aging affect the N₂O mitigation potential of biochar? A combined microcosm and field study. *Gcb Bioenergy*, vol. 9, no. 5, 953-964.
13. Hansen, S., Maehlum, J.E. & Bakken, L.R. (1993). N₂O and CH₄ fluxes in soil influenced by fertilization and tractor traffic. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, vol. 25, no. 5, 621-630.
14. Herr, C., Mannheim, T., Müller, T. & Ruser, R. (2019). Effect of cattle slurry application techniques on N₂O and NH₃ emissions from a loamy soil. *Journal of Plant Nutrition and Soil Science*, vol. 182, no. 6, 964-979.
15. Horák, J., Kondrlová, E., Igaz, D., Šimanský, V., Felber, R., Lukac, M., Balashov, E.V., Buchkina, N.P., Rizhiya, E.Y. & Jankowski, M. (2017). Biochar and biochar with N-fertilizer affect soil N₂O emission in Haplic Luvisol. *Biologia*, vol. 72, no. 9, 995-1001.
16. Hüppi, R., Felber, R., Neftel, A., Six, J. & Leifeld, J. (2015). Effect of biochar and liming on soil nitrous oxide emissions from a temperate maize cropping system. *Soil*, vol. 1, no. 2, 707-717.
17. Kesenheimer, K., Pandeya, H.R., Müller, T., Buegger, F. & Ruser, R. (2019). Nitrous oxide emissions after incorporation of winter oilseed rape (*Brassica napus* L.) residues under two different tillage treatments, *Journal of Plant Nutrition and Soil Science*, vol. 182, no. 1, 48-59.
18. Köbke, S., He, H., Böldt, M., Wang, H., Senbayram, M. & Dittert, K. (2022). Climate Overrides Effects of Fertilizer and Straw Management as Controls of Nitrous Oxide Emissions After Oilseed Rape Harvest. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 625.
19. Kontopoulou, C., Bilalis, D., Pappa, V.A., Rees, R.M. & Savvas, D. (2015). Effects of organic farming practices and salinity on yield and greenhouse gas emissions from a common bean crop, *Scientia Horticulturae*, vol. 183, 48-57.
20. Lagomarsino, A., Valagussa, M., Scotti, C., Borrelli, L., Becagli, C. & Tosca, A. (2022). Mitigation of GHG Emissions from Soils Fertilized with Livestock Chain Residues. *Agronomy*, vol. 12, no. 7, 1593.
21. Louro, A., Báez, D., García, M.I. & Cárdenas, L. (2015). Nitrous oxide emissions from forage maize production on a Humic Cambisol fertilized with mineral fertilizer or slurries in Galicia, Spain. *Geoderma Regional*, vol. 5, 54-63.
22. Ludwig, B., Jäger, N., Priesack, E. & Flessa, H. (2011). Application of the DNDC model to predict N₂O emissions from sandy arable soils with differing fertilization in a long-term experiment. *Journal of Plant Nutrition and Soil Science*, vol. 174, no. 3, 350-358.
23. Maris, S.C., Lloveras, J., Vallejo, A. & Teira-Esmatges, M.R. (2018). Effect of Stover Management and Nitrogen Fertilization on N₂O and CO₂ Emissions from Irrigated Maize in a High Nitrate Mediterranean Soil, *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution*, vol. 229, no. 11.
24. Mateo-Marín, N., Isla, R., Guillén, M. & Quílez, D. (2020). Agronomic and Environmental Implications of Substituting Pig Slurry for Synthetic Nitrogen in Mediterranean Wheat Systems. *Agronomy*, vol. 10, no. 10, 1498.

25. Meijide, A., Díez, J.A., Sánchez-Martín, L., López-Fernández, S. & Vallejo, A. (2007). Nitrogen oxide emissions from an irrigated maize crop amended with treated pig slurries and composts in a Mediterranean climate. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, vol. 121, no. 4, 383-394.
26. Meijide, A., García-Torres, L., Arce, A. & Vallejo, A. (2009). Nitrogen oxide emissions affected by organic fertilization in a non-irrigated Mediterranean barley field. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, vol. 132, no. 1-2, 106-115.
27. Nadeem, S., Hansen, S., Azzaroli Bleken, M. & Dörsch, P. (2012). N₂O emission from organic barley cultivation as affected by green manure management. *Biogeosciences*, vol. 9, no. 7, 2747-2759.
28. O'Toole, A. (2021). The agronomic and environmental effects of biochar under field conditions in Norway. *Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Faculty of Environmental Sciences and Natural Resource Management, Ås*, PhD thesis.
29. Olofsson, F. & Ernfors, M. (2022). Frost killed cover crops induced high emissions of nitrous oxide. *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 837, 155634.
30. Omirou, M., Anastopoulos, I., Fasoula, D.A. & Ioannides, I.M. (2020). The effect of chemical and organic N inputs on N₂O emission from rain-fed crops in Eastern Mediterranean. *Journal of environmental management*, vol. 270, 110755.
31. Perälä, P., Kapuinen, P., Esala, M., Tyynelä, S. & Regina, K. (2006). Influence of slurry and mineral fertiliser application techniques on N₂O and CH₄ fluxes from a barley field in southern Finland. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, vol. 117, no. 1, 71-78.
32. Plaza-Bonilla, D., Álvaro-Fuentes, J., Arrúe, J.L. & Cantero-Martínez, C. (2014). Tillage and nitrogen fertilization effects on nitrous oxide yield-scaled emissions in a rainfed Mediterranean area. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, vol. 189, 43-52.
33. Regina, K., Känkänen, H. & Singh, P. (2021). Impacts of green manure on crop yield, nitrogen leaching and nitrous oxide emissions in sandy and clay soil lysimeters. *Agricultural and Food Science* 30 (2), 53-62.
34. Rothardt, S., Fuß, R., Pahlmann, I. & Kage, H. (2021). Post-Harvest N₂O Emissions Can Be Mitigated With Organic Amendments. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 247.
35. Sanchez-Martin, L., Sanz-Cobena, A., Meijide, A., Quemada, M. & Vallejo, A. (2010). The importance of the fallow period for N₂O and CH₄ fluxes and nitrate leaching in a Mediterranean irrigated agroecosystem. *European Journal of Soil Science*, vol. 61, no. 5, 710-720.
36. Sánchez-García, M., Sánchez-Monedero, M.A. & Cayuela, M.L. (2020) N₂O emissions during Brassica oleracea cultivation: Interaction of biochar with mineral and organic fertilization. *European Journal of Agronomy*, vol. 115, 126021.
37. Sanz-Cobena, A., García-Marco, S., Quemada, M., Gabriel, J.L., Almendros, P. & Vallejo, A. (2014). Do cover crops enhance N₂O, CO₂ or CH₄ emissions from soil in Mediterranean arable systems? *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 466, 164-174.
38. Sarkodie-Addo, J., Lee, H.C. & Baggs, E.M. (2003). Nitrous oxide emissions after application of inorganic fertilizer and incorporation of green manure residues. *Soil Use and Management*, vol. 19, no. 4, 331-339.

39. Scotti, C., Bertora, C., Valagussa, M., Borrelli, L., Cabassi, G. & Tosca, A. (2022). Agroenvironmental Performances of Biochar Application in the Mineral and Organic Fertilization Strategies of a Maize–Ryegrass Forage System. *Agriculture*, vol. 12, no. 7, 925.
40. Senbayram, M., Chen, R., Wienforth, B., Herrmann, A., Kage, H., Mühling, K.H. & Dittert, K. (2014). Emission of N₂O from biogas crop production systems in Northern Germany. *BioEnergy Research*, vol. 7, no. 4, 1223-1236.
41. Skinner, C., Gattinger, A., Krauss, M., Krause, H., Mayer, J., Van Der Heijden, M.G. & Mäder, P. (2019). The impact of long-term organic farming on soil-derived greenhouse gas emissions. *Scientific reports*, vol. 9, no. 1, 1-10.
42. Sun, Z., Sängler, A., Rebensburg, P., Lentzsch, P., Wirth, S., Kaupenjohann, M. & Meyer-Aurich, A. (2017). Contrasting effects of biochar on N₂O emission and N uptake at different N fertilizer levels on a temperate sandy loam. *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 578, 557-565.
43. Sylvester-Bradley, R., Thorman, R.E., Kindred, D.R., Wynn, S.C., Smith, K.E., Rees, R.M., Topp, C., Pappa, V.A., Mortimer, N.D. & Misselbrook, T.H. (2015). Minimising Nitrous Oxide Intensities of Arable Crop Products. *AHDB Cereals & Oils Project Report*, no. 548.
44. Taghizadeh-Toosi, A., Hansen, E.M., Olesen, J.E., Baral, K.R. & Petersen, S.O. (2022). Interactive effects of straw management, tillage, and a cover crop on nitrous oxide emissions and nitrate leaching from a sandy loam soil. *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 828, 154316.
45. Thers, H., Abalos, D., Dörsch, P. & Elsgaard, L. (2020). Nitrous oxide emissions from oilseed rape cultivation were unaffected by flash pyrolysis biochar of different type, rate and field ageing. *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 724, 138140.
46. Van Groenigen, J.W., Kasper, v.G., Velthof, G.L., Van den Pol-van Dasselaar, A. & Kuikman, P.J. (2004). Nitrous oxide emissions from silage maize fields under different mineral nitrogen fertilizer and slurry applications. *Plant and Soil*, vol. 263, no. 1, 101-111.
47. Velthof, G.L. & Mosquera, J. (2011). The impact of slurry application technique on nitrous oxide emission from agricultural soils. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, vol. 140, no. 1-2, 298-308.
48. Wolf, U., Fuß, R., Höppner, F. & Flessa, H. (2014). Contribution of N₂O and NH₃ to total greenhouse gas emission from fertilization: results from a sandy soil fertilized with nitrate and biogas digestate with and without nitrification inhibitor. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems*, vol. 100, no. 1, 121-134.

6. Reference list

Abdalla, M., Hastings, A., Cheng, K., Yue, Q., Chadwick, D., Espenberg, M., Truu, J., Rees, R. M., & Smith, P. (2019). A critical review of the impacts of cover crops on nitrogen leaching, net greenhouse gas balance and crop productivity. *Global Change Biology*, 25, 2530–2543. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14644>

Acutis M, Tadiello T, Perego A, Di Guardo A, Schillaci C, Valkama E. (2021). Ex-Tract tool_1.0.xlsm. An Excel tool for the estimation of standard deviations from published articles. figshare. Software. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.14987130.v6>

Acutis, M., Tadiello, T., Perego, A., Di Guardo, A., Schillaci, C., Valkama, E. (2022). EX-TRACT: an Excel tool for the estimation of standard deviations from published articles. *Environmental Modelling and Software*, 147, 105236 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2021.105236>

Ahmad, M., Rajapaksha, A.U., Lim, J.E., Zhang, M., Bolan, N., Mohan, D., Vithanage, M., Lee, S.S., Ok, Y.S. (2014). Biochar as a sorbent for contaminant management in soil and water: a review. *Chemosphere*, 99, 19–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2013.10.071>

Bai, X., Huang, Y., Ren, W., Coyne, M., Jacinthe, P.-A., Tao, B., Hui, D., Yang, J., and Matocha, C. (2019). Responses of soil carbon sequestration to climate-smart agriculture practices: A meta-analysis, *Global Change Biology*, 25, 2591–2606. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14658>

Basche, A.D., Miguez, F.E., Kaspar, T.C. and Castellano, M.J. (2014). Do cover crops increase or decrease nitrous oxide emissions? A meta-analysis. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 69, 471-482. <https://doi:10.2489/jswc.69.6.471>

Bolinder, M.A., Crotty, F., Elsen, A., Frac, M., Kismányoky, T., Lipiec, J., Tits, M., Tóth, Z., Kätterer, T. (2020). The effect of crop residues, cover crops, manures and nitrogen fertilization on soil organic carbon changes in agroecosystems: a synthesis of reviews. *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 25, 929-952. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11027-020-09916-3>

Borchard, N., Schirrmann, M., Luz Cayuela, M., Kammann, C., Wrage-Moennig, N., Estavillo, J.M., Fuertes-Mendizabal, T., Sigua, G., Spokas, K., Ippolito, J.A., Novak, J. (2019). Biochar, soil and landuse interactions that reduce nitrate leaching and N₂O emissions: A meta-analysis. *Science of the Total Environment*, 651, 2354-2364. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.060>

Borenstein, M., Hedges, L., Higgins, J., Rothstein, H. (2009). Introduction to Meta-Analysis. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.

Carter, M.S., Sørensen, P., Petersen, S.O. Ma, X., Ambus, P. (2014) Effects of green manure storage and incorporation methods on nitrogen release and N₂O emissions after soil application. *Biology and Fertility of Soils*, 50, 1233–1246. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-014-0936-5>

Cayuela, M.L., van Zwieten, L., Singh, B.P., Jeffery, S., Roig, A., Sánchez-Monedero, M.A., (2014). Biochar's role in mitigating soil nitrous oxide emissions: A review and meta-analysis. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 191, 5–16.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2013.10.009>

Chen, H., Li, X., Hu, F., Shi, W. (2013). Soil nitrous oxide emissions following crop residue addition: a meta-analysis. *Global Change Biology*, 19, 2956-2964.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12274>

Efron, B., and R. Tibshirani. (1986). Bootstrap methods for standard errors, confidence intervals, and other measures of statistical accuracy. *Statistical Science*, 1, 54–77.

Essich, L., Nkebiwe, P.M., Schneider, M. & Ruser, R. (2020) Is crop residue removal to reduce N₂O emissions driven by quality or quantity? A field study and meta-analysis,

Agriculture, 10, 546. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture10110546>

Fan, X., Chen, X., Chen, T., Liu, X., Song, Y., Tan, S., Chen, Y., Yan, P., Wang, X. (2023).

Effects of substituting synthetic nitrogen with organic amendments on crop yield, net greenhouse gas emissions and carbon footprint: A global meta-analysis. *Field Crops Research*, 301, p.109035. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2023.109035>

Gross, A., Bromm, T., Glaser, B. (2021) Soil Organic Carbon Sequestration after Biochar Application: A Global Meta-Analysis. *Agronomy*, 11, 2474.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy11122474>

Guenet, B., Gabrielle, B., Chenu, C., Arrouays, D., Balesdent, J., Bernoux, M., ... & Ciais, P. (2021). Can N₂O emissions offset the benefits from soil organic carbon storage? *Global Change Biology*, 27, 237-256. <https://doi.org/10.1111/GCB.15342>

Han, Z., Walter, M.T. and Drinkwater, L.E. (2017). N₂O emissions from grain cropping systems: a meta-analysis of the impacts of fertilizer-based and ecologically-based nutrient management strategies. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems*, 107, 335-355.

Hedges, L.V., Gurevitch, J., Curtis, P.S. (1999). The meta-analysis of response ratios in experimental ecology. *Ecology*. 80(4):1150–1156. <https://doi.org/10.2307/177062>.

Jeffery, S., Abalos, D., Prodana, M., Bastos, A.C., van Groenigen, J.W., Hungate, B.A., Verheijen, F. (2017). Biochar boosts tropical but not temperate crop yields. *Environmental Research Letters*, 12, 053001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aa67bd>

Jian, J., Du, X., Reiter, M. S., and Stewart, R. D. (2020). A meta-analysis of global cropland soil carbon changes due to cover cropping, *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 143, 107735. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2020.107735>

Kong, F., Li, Q., Yang, Z. and Chen, Y. (2023). Does the application of biogas slurry reduce soil N₂O emissions and increase crop yield? –A systematic review. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 342, p.118339.

Koricheva, J., Gurevitch, J., Mengersen, K. (Eds.), 2013. Handbook of meta-analysis in ecology and evolution. Princeton University Press, Princeton.

Lehmann, J., Abiven, S., Kleber, M., Pan, G., Singh, B.P., Sohi, S.P., Zimmerman, A.R. (2015). Persistence of biochar in soil, in: Lehmann, J., Joseph, S. (Eds.), *Biochar for Environmental Management: Science, Technology and Implementation*. Earthscan, Routledge, London, 236–282.

Lehmann, J., Gaunt, J., Rondon, M. (2006). Bio-char Sequestration in Terrestrial Ecosystems – A Review. *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 11, 395–419. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11027-005-9006-5>

Lehmann, J., Joseph, S. (2015). *Biochar for Environmental Management: Science, Technology, and Implementation*, 2nd ed. Routledge, New York.

Lugato, E., Leip, A. & Jones, A. (2018) Mitigation potential of soil carbon management overestimated by neglecting N₂O emissions. *Nature Climate Change*, 8, 219–223. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-018-0087-z>

Maillard, É., Angers, D.A. (2014). Animal manure application and soil organic carbon stocks: A meta-analysis. *Global Change Biology*, 20, 666–679. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12438>

Mavridis, D., Moustaki, I., Wall, M., Salanti, G. (2017). Detecting outlying studies in meta-regression models using a forward search algorithm: Forward Search in Meta-analysis. *Research Synthesis Methods*, 8, 199–211. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1197>.

Metzger, M.J., Bunce, R.G.H., Jongman, R.H.G., Múcher, C.A., Watkins, J.W. (2005). A climatic stratification of the environment of Europe. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 14, 549–563. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00190.x>

Metzger, M.J., Bunce, R.G.H., Jongman, R.H.G., Sayre, R., Trabucco, A., Zomer, R. (2013). A high-resolution bioclimate map of the world: A unifying framework for global biodiversity research and monitoring. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 22, 630–638. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.12022>

Muhammad, I., Sainju, U.M., Zhao, F., Khan, A., Ghimire, R., Fu, X., Wang, J. (2019). Regulation of soil CO₂ and N₂O emissions by cover crops: A meta-analysis. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 192, 103–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2019.04.020>

Nett, L., Sradnick, A., Fuß, R., Flessa, H., Fink, M. (2016). Emissions of nitrous oxide and ammonia after cauliflower harvest are influenced by soil type and crop residue management. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems*, 106, 217–231.

Rittl, T., Thiébeau, P., Recous, S., Rees, R., Abalos, D., Ahuja, I., Smith, K.E., Topp, C.F.E., Ernfors, M., Bleken, M.A., Thorman, R.E., Pappa, V.a.H., S (2022) *Secondary data of N₂O emissions associated with the return of crop residues from field studies*. <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/43610/>

Rosenberg, M.S., D.C. Adams, Gurevitch, J. (2000). *Metawin: Statistical Software for Meta-analysis, Version 2.1*. Sinauer Associates, Inc, Sunderland, MA, USA.

Sandén, T., Spiegel, H., Stüger, H.P., Schlatter, N., Haslmayr, H.P., Zavattaro, L., Grignani, C., Bechini, L., D' Hose, T., Molendijk, L., Pecio, A. (2018). European long-term field

experiments: knowledge gained about alternative management practices. *Soil Use Management*, 34, 167-176. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sum.12421>

Schneider, C. A., Rasband, W. S., Eliceiri, K. W. (2012). NIH Image to ImageJ: 25 years of image analysis. *Nature Methods*, 9(7), 671–675. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.2089>

Shakoor, A., Shakoor, S., Rehman, A., Ashraf, F., Abdullah, M., Shahzad, S.M., Farooq, T.H., Ashraf, M., Manzoor, M.A., Altaf, M.M., Altaf, M.A. (2021a) Effect of animal manure, crop type, climate zone, and soil attributes on greenhouse gas emissions from agricultural soils-A global meta-analysis. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 278, p.124019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124019>

Shakoor, A., Shahzad, S.M., Chatterjee, N., Arif, M.S., Farooq, T.H., Altaf, M.M., Tufail, M.A., Dar, A.A., Mehmood, T. (2021b) Nitrous oxide emission from agricultural soils: Application of animal manure or biochar? A global meta-analysis. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 285, 112170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112170>

Siedt, M., Schäffer, A., Smith, K.E., Nabel, M., Roß-Nickoll, M. and van Dongen, J.T. (2021). Comparing straw, compost, and biochar regarding their suitability as agricultural soil amendments to affect soil structure, nutrient leaching, microbial communities, and the fate of pesticides. *Science of the Total Environment*, 751, 141607. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141607>

Smith, P. (2016). Soil carbon sequestration and biochar as negative emission technologies. *Global Change Biology*, 22, 1315–1324. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13178>

Sterne, J.A.C., Egger, M. (2001). Funnel plots for detecting bias in meta-analysis: Guidelines on choice of axis. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 10, 1046-55. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0895-4356\(01\)00377-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0895-4356(01)00377-8)

Tiefenbacher A., Sandén T., Haslmayr H.-P., Miloczki J., Wenzel W., Spiegel H. (2021). Optimizing Carbon Sequestration in Croplands: A Synthesis. *Agronomy*, 11, 882. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy11050882>

Thorman, R.E., Nicholson, F.A., Topp, C.F., Bell, M.J., Cardenas, L.M., Chadwick, D.R., Cloy, J.M., Misselbrook, T.H., Rees, R.M., Watson, C.J. and Williams, J.R. (2020). Towards country-specific nitrous oxide emission factors for manures applied to arable and grassland soils in the UK. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 62. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2020.00062>

Verhoeven, E., Pereira, E., Decock, C., Suddick, E., Angst, T., Six, J. (2017). Toward a Better Assessment of Biochar-Nitrous Oxide Mitigation Potential at the Field Scale. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 46, 237–246. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2016.10.0396>

Wang, M., Pendall, E., Fang, C., Li, B. and Nie, M. (2018). A global perspective on agroecosystem nitrogen cycles after returning crop residue. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 266, 49-54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2018.07.019>

Wei, Z., Ying, H., Guo, X., Zhuang M., Cui Z., Zhang F. (2020) Substitution of Mineral Fertilizer with Organic Fertilizer in Maize Systems: A Meta-Analysis of Reduced Nitrogen and Carbon Emissions. *Agronomy*, 10, 1149. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy10081149>

Woolf, D., Amonette, J.E., Street-Perrott, F.A., Lehmann, J., Joseph, S. (2010). Sustainable biochar to mitigate global climate change. *Nature Communications*, 1, 56. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms1053>

Xia, L., Lam, S.K., Wolf, B., Kiese, R., Chen, D. and Butterbach-Bahl, K. (2018). Trade-offs between soil carbon sequestration and reactive nitrogen losses under straw return in global agroecosystems. *Global Change Biology*, 24, 5919-5932. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14466>

Zhou, M., Zhu, B., Wang, S., Zhu, X., Vereecken, H., Brüggemann, N. (2017). Stimulation of N₂O emission by manure application to agricultural soils may largely offset carbon benefits: a global meta-analysis. *Global Change Biology*, 23, 4068–4083. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13648>